

A New Method to Determine the Bending Rigidities of Anisotropic Plates

Y. Masuda

Faculty of Engineering, Ibaraki University, Naka-narusawa 4-12-1, Hitachi, Ibaraki 316, Japan

ABSTRACT

A new test method is presented for bending rigidities determination of orthotropic plates as well as laminated composite materials. The test technique employs a large plate subjected to three-point loading normal to the plane of the plate. The out-of-plane deflection to the various bending rigidities and the loading conditions is analyzed to determine a suitable method for bending characteristic measurement.

The results obtained are summarized as follows: (1) To determine the principal directions of the plate, bending test is carried out in several loading directions ϕ against its reference axis and relative deflections $h(s)$ are measured at a constant measuring distance s . Then the principal directions can be determined by finding out the symmetric points of the $h-\phi$ diagram. (2) After the principal directions have been determined, bending test is carried out in the directions of 0° , 45° and 90° to the principal axis, and the relative deflections are measured as a function of measuring distance s . Then the basic bending rigidities can be obtained from the integral values of $h(s)$.

The validity of the test method is demonstrated by conducting the test for a CFRP plate.

INTRODUCTION

Measuring the elastic properties of anisotropic materials has become an important problem with the development of composite materials. The elastic constants of anisotropic plates can be determined by conducting tensile and bending tests for coupon specimens cut out in some directions. But this methods can't be applied to practical structures as a non-destructive testing technique, whereas determining the elastic properties of practical structures and evaluating its ability in actual use are more essential for composite materials.

The fundamental elastic constants of an orthotropic plate can be expressed by four in-plane elastic constants and four bending rigidities. When the construction of the plate and the properties of these constituent laminae are well known, the bending rigidities can be calculated from the in-plane elastic constants (1,2). But in practice, these are often treated as independent constants to each other and determined experimentally.

Considerable studies have been made on ordinary or special testing techniques for experimental characterizations and various standard methods such as

the ASTM standards have been defined, in which most characterizations are to be made by using the specimens which were cut out from original plates or structures (3~9).

In this paper a new method to determine the bending rigidities is suggested and its application results is demonstrated. In this method, three-point bending test is conducted for a large test plate, then the measured deflections are analyzed and reduced to determine the principal directions and the bending rigidities.

The method will be applicable to practical structures because of unnecessary cut out specimens.

THREE-POINT BENDING OF ORTHOTROPIC PLATE

A x-y coordinate system is assumed in the principal directions of an orthotropic plate and the deflection of the plate is denoted by w. Then the relation between the internal forces acting on a cross section of the plate and the deflection is expressed by

$$\begin{pmatrix} M_x \\ M_y \\ H_{xy} \end{pmatrix} = - \begin{bmatrix} D_{11} & D_{12} & 0 \\ D_{12} & D_{22} & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & D_{33} \end{bmatrix} \begin{pmatrix} \frac{\partial^2 w}{\partial x^2} \\ \frac{\partial^2 w}{\partial y^2} \\ \frac{\partial^2 w}{\partial x \partial y} \end{pmatrix} \quad (1)$$

where M and H are the bending and twisting moment per unit length respectively as shown in Figure 1 and D_{ij} are the bending rigidities in the x-y axes.

The rigidity in a direction ϕ , D_ϕ , can be calculated by

$$D_\phi = D_1 \cos^4 \phi + 2D_2 \cos^2 \phi \sin^2 \phi + D_3 \sin^4 \phi \quad (2)$$

where $D_1 \equiv D_{11}$, $D_2 \equiv D_{12}$, $D_3 \equiv D_{22} + 2D_{33}$

If the rigidities in the directions of 0° , 45° and 90° are known, then the basic rigidities D_1, D_2 and D_3 are calculated by equations (3)

$$D_1 = D_0, \quad D_2 = D_{00}, \quad D_3 = \frac{1}{2} (4D_{45} - D_0 - D_{00}) \quad (3)$$

The differential equation related to w is described as

$$D_1 \frac{\partial^4 w}{\partial x^4} + 2D_2 \frac{\partial^4 w}{\partial x^2 \partial y^2} + D_3 \frac{\partial^4 w}{\partial y^4} = Q(x, y) \quad (4)$$

where Q is a vertically distributed load to the plate (1).

As shown in Figure 2, when the plate is simply supported along the two lines which are parallel to a y'-axis and subjected to a linear uniform load which acts along the center line of the supports, the plate becomes a cylindrical bending state and the deflection of the loading line is

$$w_\phi = \frac{\bar{P} l^4}{48 D_\phi} \quad (5)$$

in which a x'-y' coordinate system is assumed in a direction ϕ to the x-y axes, l is the span length and \bar{P} is the load per unit length.

In this case, the deflection along the x'-axis is the same as the deflection of a beam of bending rigidity D_ϕ under three-point bending.

When the plate is supported at the points B and C which are located at the positions $l/2$, $-l/2$ on the x'-axis and subjected to a load P at the center as shown in Figure 3, the deflection w is expressed as

$$w(x, y) = v(x, y) - \frac{1}{2} [v(x - \xi, y + \eta) + v(x + \xi, y - \eta)] \quad (6)$$

$$\xi = \frac{1}{2} l \sin \phi, \quad \eta = \frac{1}{2} l \cos \phi$$

where the function v is the virtual solution of the hypothetical problem in which the infinite plate is subjected to the load P only at the origin without any

Fig. 1. Moments and transverse shear forces.

Fig. 2. Cylindrical bending of an orthotropic plate.

Fig. 3. Bending of an orthotropic plate subjected to three-point loading.

support. The deflections at the points A', B' and C' which are located parallel to the y'-axis at distance s from A, B and C respectively are denoted by $w_{A'}$, $w_{B'}$ and $w_{C'}$ and the deflection at A' measured from the line drawn through the points B' and C' is defined as relative deflection under the loading direction ϕ , then the relative deflection, $h(s)$, is

$$h(s) = w_{A'} - \frac{1}{2}(w_{B'} + w_{C'}) \quad (7)$$

Substituting equation (6) in equation (7), the relative deflection expressed by the function v is

$$h(s) = \frac{1}{4}(6v_{A'} - 4v_{B'} - 4v_{C'} + v_{B''} + v_{C''}) \quad (8)$$

where B'' and C'' are the points of $(1, s)$, $(-1, s)$ by x'-y' axes respectively and the subscripts A'~C'' indicate the points at which the function v is defined. Adopting a polar coordinate system $x = r \cos \theta$, $y = r \sin \theta$, the function v can be calculated as follows:

(1) for isotropic plates, $D_1 = D_2 = D_3 \equiv D$

$$v_{iso} = \frac{P}{16\pi D} r^2 \ln r^2$$

(2) for special orthotropic plates, $D_3^2 = D_1 D_2$

$$v = \frac{P}{16\pi D_1 \sqrt{\mu}} r^2 \left(\cos^2 \theta + \frac{\sin^2 \theta}{\mu} \right) \ln r^2 \left(\cos^2 \theta + \frac{\sin^2 \theta}{\mu} \right)$$

$$\text{where } \mu = \frac{D_3}{D_1} \left(= \sqrt{\frac{D_2}{D_1}} \right)$$

(3) for orthotropic plates, $D_3^2 > D_1 D_2$

$$v = \frac{P}{16\pi D_1} \frac{1}{\mu_2 - \mu_1} [v^1(\mu_2) - v^1(\mu_1)]$$

$$\text{where } v^1(\mu) = 2\sqrt{\mu} r^2 \left[\left(\cos^2 \theta - \frac{\sin^2 \theta}{\mu} \right) \ln r^2 \left(\cos^2 \theta + \frac{\sin^2 \theta}{\mu} \right) - \frac{4\cos \theta \sin \theta}{\sqrt{\mu}} \tan^{-1} \frac{\sin \theta}{\sqrt{\mu} \cos \theta} + \frac{2\sin^2 \theta}{\mu} \right]$$

$$\mu_{1,2} = \frac{D_2 \pm \sqrt{D_2^2 - D_1 D_2}}{D_1}$$

(4) for orthotropic plates, $D_2^2 < D_1 D_2$,

$$v = \frac{P}{16\pi D_1} r^2 \left[\frac{(\mu_2 \cos^2 \theta + \sin^2 \theta) \sin \beta}{\mu_2 \sqrt{\mu_2}} \left\{ -4 \sin^2 \theta \right. \right. \\ \left. \left. + \ln r^4 \left(\cos^4 \theta + \frac{2\mu_1}{\mu_2^2} \cos^2 \theta \sin^2 \theta + \frac{1}{\mu_2^2} \sin^4 \theta \right) \right\} \right. \\ \left. + \frac{(\mu_2 \cos^2 \theta - \sin^2 \theta) 2 \cos \beta}{\mu_2 \sqrt{\mu_2}} \tan^{-1} \frac{-\mu_2 \sin^2 \theta}{\mu_2^2 \cos^2 \theta + \mu_1 \sin^2 \theta} \right. \\ \left. - \frac{2 \cos \theta \sin \theta}{\mu_2} \ln \frac{\mu_2 \cos^2 \theta - 2\sqrt{\mu_1} \sin \beta \cos \theta \sin \theta + \sin^2 \theta}{\mu_2 \cos^2 \theta + 2\sqrt{\mu_1} \sin \beta \cos \theta \sin \theta + \sin^2 \theta} \right] \\ \text{where } \mu_1 = \frac{D_2}{D_1}, \mu_2 = \frac{\sqrt{D_1 D_2 - D_2^2}}{D_1}, \mu_3 = \frac{D_2}{D_1} (= \sqrt{\mu_1^2 + \mu_2^2}) \\ \beta = \frac{1}{2} \tan^{-1} \frac{\sqrt{D_1 D_2 - D_2^2}}{D_2} (= \frac{1}{2} \tan^{-1} \frac{\mu_2}{\mu_1}) \quad (9)$$

Thus the deflection w and the relative deflection h of infinite plates can be calculated by substituting equations (9) in equations (6) and (8).

Using a function $F(\alpha)$, the relative deflection is expressed as

$$h(\alpha) = \frac{Pl^2}{D_1} F(\alpha), \quad \alpha = \frac{s}{l} \quad (10)$$

in which a dimensionless distance parameter $\alpha = s/l$ is used instead of the distance s . Figure 4 shows the values of the function F calculated for some orthotropic constants. From these results, it is obvious that

Fig. 4. Relative deflection coefficient F versus distance parameter α .

Fig. 5. Coefficient F versus loading direction ϕ for $\alpha = 0$.

the relative deflections decrease rapidly as α increase and become nearly zero at $\alpha = 3 \sim 4$, though there are some difference according to their constants.

The relative deflection at the point $\alpha = 0$, for $D_2^2 < D_1 D_2$ is

$$h(0) = \frac{Pl^2}{D_1} \frac{2\sqrt{D_2/D_1} \sin \beta}{32\pi \sqrt{(D_1 D_2 - D_2^2)/D_1}} \left(\sin^2 \phi + \frac{\cos^2 \phi}{\sqrt{D_2/D_1}} \right) \ln 4, \quad \beta = \frac{1}{2} \tan^{-1} \frac{\sqrt{D_1 D_2 - D_2^2}}{D_2} \quad (11)$$

In this equation $h(0)$ becomes a constant value irrespective of the loading direction ϕ for the special case $D_1 = D_2$.

$F(0)$ - ϕ diagrams calculated for some constants are shown in Figure 5, in which the F - ϕ diagrams for $D_2/D_1 = 1.0$ are indicated as constant values as mentioned above.

By the Maxwell's reciprocal relationship, it is proved that the relative

deflection $h_{A'B'C'}$ which is defined as the relative deflection at A', B' and C' under the three-point bending at A, B and C is equals to the relative deflection h_{ABC} which is defined as the relative deflection at A, B and C under the three-point bending at A', B' and C'. The integral of $h_{A'B'C'}$ along the y' -axis is expressed as

$$\int_{-\infty}^{\infty} h(\alpha) d\alpha = \int_{-\infty}^{\infty} h_{A'B'C'} \frac{ds}{l} = \int_{-\infty}^{\infty} h_{ABC} \frac{ds}{l}$$

The last integral is equals to the deflection of the plate which is simply supported and applied a linear distributed load of intensity P/l per unit length as shown in Figure 2. Thus the bending rigidity in the direction ϕ is expressed as

$$D_{\phi} = \frac{\bar{P}l^3}{48} \int_{-\infty}^{\infty} h(s) \frac{ds}{l} = \frac{Pl^3}{48} \int_{-\infty}^{\infty} h(s) \frac{ds}{l} \quad (12)$$

From this equation the rigidity in an arbitrary direction can be calculated from the integral of the relative deflection by conducting the three-point bending test of the same direction and measuring the relative deflection along the y' -axis. In above discussion, it is assumed that the plate is infinitely large, but the method may be also applicable both for a sufficiently large finite plate and for the case where the direction of the y' -axis is perpendicular to the edges of a finite plate. The method is also applicable for an arbitrary anisotropic plate.

DECISION OF PRINCIPAL DIRECTIONS AND APPROXIMATE CALCULATION OF INTEGRAL OF RELATIVE DEFLECTION

When a large plate for which the principal directions and the bending rigidities are to be determined is given, the first thing to be done is to decide the principal directions.

It is obvious from equations (9) that h - ϕ diagrams are symmetrical in relation to the points of $\phi = 0^\circ, 90^\circ$ when the load P and the distant parameter α are constant. Therefor, after conducting the three-point bending test under the constant load in various loading directions and measuring the relative deflections at the constant distance s (i.e. constant α), the principal directions are decided as the angles to which the h - ϕ diagram become symmetrical.

The measuring position of the relative deflections must not be $\alpha = 0$, because at this position the h - ϕ diagram shows a constant value in the special case of $D_1 = D_2$. Some F - ϕ diagrams are shown in Figure 6, here α is used as a parameter. The variation of the value of F becomes large for large value of α , though the value of h itself becomes small. So measurements at large α not always mean accurate decision of the principal directions.

Figure 7 shows the relations between the absolute values of the difference of the value F at $\phi = 0^\circ, 45^\circ$ and 90° and the distance parameter α . As a temporary standard, it may be recommended that most accurate decision of the principal directions will be made when the measurements of the relative deflections are conducted at the position at which distance the maximum value of the ordinate in Figure 7 is attained. Although the position is vary according to their orthotropic rigidities, in the case when the principal directions are to be decided for a plate which rigidities are unknown, the most suitable measuring position of the relative deflections is considered to be $\alpha = 1/2 - 1$.

Once the principal directions have been decided, the basic bending rigidities D_1, D_2 and D_3 are calculated from the results of the three-point bending test of $0^\circ, 45^\circ$ and 90° in which the relative deflections are measured along the y' -axis.

It is estimated that the difference of less than about 3 percent will be expected between the deflection calculated by infinite assumption and that of a finite plate of a size of about 20 times the span l . Decision of principal directions may be possible for larger plates than this.

It is expected that a calculation of D_1, D_2 and D_3 can be derived by solving the equations (8)~(9) for D_1, D_2 and D_3 , but this considerably complex procedure may not results in a practical use.

Fig. 6. Coefficient F versus loading direction ϕ for $\alpha = 0 \sim 1.5$

Fig. 7. Variation of difference of coefficient F at $\phi = 0^\circ, 45^\circ, 90^\circ$.

Table 1. Comparison of approximate values of integral of relative deflection coefficient F for $A = 2$.

D_2/D_1	D_3/D_1	ϕ	$\int_{-\infty}^{\infty} F d\alpha$	$\int_A^A F d\alpha$	Additional term	Error (%)
0.5	0.5	0°	0.0208	0.0182	0.0027	0.45
0.5	0.5	90°	0.0417	0.0343	0.0077	0.73
2.0	2.0	0°	0.0208	0.0160	0.0051	0.88
2.0	2.0	90°	0.0104	0.0086	0.0018	0.33

Some difficulty will arise when the numerical integral of the relative deflections is calculated because of its integral interval $(-\infty, \infty)$. In the case of isotropic plates, the function $F(\alpha)$ is approximated as $F \approx 0.0037/\alpha^2 + 0(1/\alpha^4)$ for large α . Using the assumption that the function $F(\alpha)$ for arbitrary orthotropic will be approximated as $F \approx C_1/(\alpha + C_2)^2$ for large α , the integral of the relative deflection can be expressed as

$$\int_{-\infty}^{\infty} F(\alpha) d\alpha \approx \int_A^A F(\alpha) d\alpha - \left. \frac{4F^2}{F'} \right|_{\alpha=A} \quad (13)$$

where the integral of interval $(-A, A)$ is integrated numerically from experimental results and the last term (additional term) is calculated from C_1 and C_2 which are determined from the assumption that the values of the function F and its differential coefficient F' at the point $\alpha = \pm A$ by the approximated expression should equal to the corresponding values by experimental results.

Table 1 shows the integral values of a finite interval $(-A, A)$ for $A = 2$, additional terms, errors compared to the infinite integral for some orthotropic plates.

As was stated previously, when the assumption of infinite plate is not valid, numerical integral should be made about whole the range of the plate.

EXPERIMENTAL RESULTS

To ensure and demonstrate the availability of this method, experiments were carried out for a CFRP plate which was constructed from carbon fabric and plain woven glass fabric and polyester resin. The size of the plate was 1000 mm x 1000 mm wide, 3.7 mm thickness.

The three-point bending test was done by using a device which was made from angle bars. A dial-gage-mounted device was also constructed to measure the relative deflections. Figure 8 shows the plate tested by these devices.

The test was conducted by a constant span length $l = 100$ mm. The initial load 9.4 kgf was applied, then the load was increased to 39.7 kgf. The relative deflection through this load increase 30.3 kgf was read by the device which was placed at a distance s from the loading line.

Figure 9 shows the $h-\phi$ diagrams for $s = 50, 100$ mm ($\alpha = 1/2, 1$). It is obvious that these diagrams are symmetrical in relation to the points $\phi = 0^\circ$ and 90° which are the principal directions of this plate.

T: Test plate
 L: Three- point loading device
 D: Relative deflection measuring device

Fig. 8. Three-point bending test for a CFRP plate

Fig. 9. h - ϕ diagrams by experiment for a CFRP plate.

Fig. 10. h - α diagrams by experiment for a CFRP plate.

Figure 10 shows the h - α diagrams for $\phi = 0^\circ, 45^\circ$ and 90° . In this experiments, it is considered that the plate is not as large as to be treated as an infinite plate. Numerical integral was made for the relative deflections of $0^\circ, 45^\circ$ and 90° directions to calculate the basic bending rigidities, and these results are shown in Table 2.

The Table also shows the rigidities by ordinary test method in which coupon specimens cut out from the plate after the three-point bending test were used.

It is observed that the rigidities by the three-point bending method are a little higher than those by the ordinary test and the same tendency were observed in other experiments for some orthotropic plates. The sources of these errors are considered to be reduced to following causes: One is the friction in the loading mechanisms which will make the actual load lower and another one is the friction in the dial gage which will also bring a smaller measurement of the relative deflection, especially for large α . Both of them will serve as causes of higher

Table 2. Comparison of rigidities of a CFRP plate by experiments.

	D ₀ ^o	D ₄₅ ^o	D ₉₀ ^o
From integral of h(α)	7680	3860	2830
Ordinary bending test (Span:100mm, Specimen width:60mm)	6700	3220	2330

(kgf-mm)

values of rigidities.

More accurate measurements will be expected by this method, if these defects on testing technique are improved. Also accurate measurements will be expected by using a wider span length l , when the edges of quadrate plates are parallel to the testing direction.

CONCLUSIONS

Materials properties of laminate composites depend not only on the kinds of constituent materials but also on its arrangement and fabricating method, which make the testing of practical structures more difficult and more important compared to ordinary structures.

In this paper, a new test method to determine the principal directions and the bending rigidities of orthotropic plates was suggested and an experimental results for a CFRP plate is demonstrated.

The results obtained are as follows: (1) The directions of the principal axes of a large orthotropic plate can be determined by finding the symmetrical points of the $h-\phi$ diagram which is measured at a constant distance $\alpha=1/2-1$ by the three-point bending test of various loading angles ϕ under a constant load. (2) The basic bending rigidities D_1 , D_2 and D_3 can be calculated from the integral of the relative deflections of 0° , 45° and 90° directions.

By this method, bending rigidities of large plates can be measured without cutting out the test pieces.

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